

Participant N°	Participant organization name	Short name	Country
1 (Coordinator)	Universidad del País Vasco / Euskal Herriko Unibertsitatea (Beneficiary)	UPV/EHU	Spain
2	Kemijski Institut (Beneficiary)	NIC	Slovenia
3	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique CNRS (Beneficiary)	CNRS	France
4	Universitetet i Oslo (Beneficiary)	UiO	Norway
5	Universita Degli Studi di Torino (Beneficiary)	UNITO	Italy
6	Johnson Matthey (Associated Partner)	JM	United Kingdom
7	ProfMOF AS (Associated Partner)	PMOF	Norway
8	Genoscope (Associated Partner)	Gen	France
9	Yellow Research (Associated Partner)	YR	The Netherlands
10	Universite de Lille (Associated Partner)	Univ-Lille	France
11	Univerza V Ljubljani (Associated Partner)	Uni-lj	Slovenia